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Report on the state-of-the-art in
autobiography and selfhood
in Islamic societies
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In this first deliverable we will provide the state of the art on “Narratives of the Self” based on the reading reports and reflections on the keynote and literature of the MIDA online school. Whereas the MIDA-school provided the three ESR’s with core literature as suggested by the keynote speakers - in addition to their keynotes - the ESR’s also did additional reading in order to relate the general theme to their specific topics.

In this introduction we reflect on the core theme and the input from the MIDA online school. Next, the three ESR’s will relate the core issues and additional reading to their specific topics.

Introduction

The idea behind the theme of this work package is to investigate how the performance of selfhood is transformed due to technological innovations like the digital age. How is the ‘self’ performed? Which aspects of the self are performed and through which media? What is the impact of different means and media on this performance of the self and what are the social-political and religious consequences of these changing ways of performing the self?

During the online MIDA-school several presentations showed that aspects of self that are usually hidden can be staged online, whether this pertains to religion or non-religion, sexuality, LGTB-rights, artistic expression and political issues and citizenship. The aspects of the self that are more often staged online are particularly related to the three so-called “taboo zones”, to wit, politics, religion, and sexuality. With that it questions dominant forms of authority, whether parental, communal, religious or political. It questions norms regarding gender and sexuality, it raises questions regarding dominant discourses on religion and it questions the legitimacy of political regimes. This explains the importance of the topic of WP 4 for WP 1 and the reason to combine these two WP’s in the online school.

Introduction

These new forms of self-expression seem to entail a claim to space for a more individualized form of selfhood. The Muslim / Arab world is usually characterized as stressing communal or relational forms of identities and putting less emphasis on individualized selfhood in comparison to the West. Of course this is an assumption we need to investigate, it is a question mark.

The keynote and study by Suad Joseph (2005) are important in questioning this notion of the 'modern individualized self'. As Suad Joseph has shown diverse theoretical streams on the Middle East fed into the idea that the Arab region did not have a modern notion of self – and that this 'failure' partly explained its 'dysfunctional' development. Prime reasons offered for this lack of an adequate modern self was related to Islam and to patriarchy. With regard to Islam the dominant discourse was the idea about the submission of women. And we owe to the important work of Saba Mahmood that we are able to rethink "submission" by women to religious norms as an active ethical engagement in cultivating a pious self. With regard to patriarchy Suad Joseph has developed the notion of patriarchal connectivity and the relational self. Similar to Mahmood (2005)

who showed how agency is developed within certain historical and political formations and context the same can be said about notions of the self whether relational or individualized. It is also the broader political context of the state which impact on the developments of certain forms of selfhood. So if we study selfhood and expression of the self we need to reflect of the notion of selfhood itself and how this very notion is a product of historical, political, social and religious configurations.

This raises the question how to study these expressions of the self, whether in the forms of autobiographies, biographies, artist productions, photos and political expressions, etc. whether in the form of text, images, or interview fragments. The two keynotes by professor Hurley-Lambert and professor Buitelaar were excellent examples and provided helpful ways forward how to engage in such a project. Whereas professor Hurley-Lambert clearly showed how texts like autobiographies are never self-evident and need to be studied within their production context: how are they produced; for whom; how are these text influenced by other people like editors, translators. So text and context but not only how the context is reflected in the text but how it actively shaping the text.

Introduction

Professor Buitelaar presented us with an in-depth methodology how to read and study in a detailed way the narrative in the shape of an autobiography or an interview fragment: The DST is an analytical tool to study self-narratives and examine how desires, views, feelings and experiences are informed by the various cultural discourses and accompanying power relations that the self is embedded in. The DST enables the study of the multiplicity of voices and I- positions. Here the context is not that much external to the text and influencing it or being influenced by it but the external positions are part of the text. It also encourages us to look for the multiple and changing expression of self/ or voices and I positions which are never stable or singular. DST is also an analytical tool to study intersectionality in self-narratives, which is an important approach in several of the ESR's projects.

Accordingly the three keynotes related to “Narratives of the Self” formed overlapping but also widening circles of contextual understanding of selfhood:

- 1→ the self in the sense of ‘you – yourself’, situated in a particular personal-historical conjunction;
- 2→ the text one studies - looking for multiple and shifting expressions of the self-other and identity positions within the text;
- 3→ the encouragement to include in the investigations how these text are produced and shaped within a certain context and time frame of production and consumption of these text thus critically examining the text and not taking it at face value ;
- 4→ the importance to include the larger context of the social cultural and historical forces including the state regarding notions we use like the self and study its genealogy and intertwinement with dominant western notions of the self.

Part 1.

Pre-Modern Arabic Autobiography: The Genre and Its Characteristics

By Mohamed El-Moursi (ESR 1)

The recognition and identification of autobiographical writings in pre-modern Arabic tradition have been judged by modern notions of autobiography until the late twentieth century. Several texts, as a result, were rejected due to their limited disclosure of intimate personal details (Navarro, 2015). Pre-modern Arabic autobiographies were not only more numerous than usually presumed, but they were also an established literary genre with its own textual practices, ways of transmission, motivations for writings, and conventions of self-representation. By the twelfth century, there was a general awareness of the autobiographical writing as a distinct category of writing. From the ninth century on, these autobiographies started to be spread across generations and marked desperate regions of the medieval Muslim world. The genre continued to be in use across different historical periods, and was still common practice in the twentieth century (Reynolds et al, 2001).

Despite their wide temporal and geographical scope, these writings stand in relation to other types of texts, portraying common features that apply to all texts classified as 'autobiography.' It could be argued that the construction of autobiographical memoirs emerged from the development of biographical writings. Oral reports, or akhbār, were the earliest form in which the tribesmen narrate their memorable moments in their lives, but it did not go far enough to be a summary of one's life. With the advent of writing, the biographers were first constructed from the accumulation and combination of the oral reports. The dominant pattern within these texts is the interlacement of prose and poetry, woven into one holistic style. This will remain one of the main stylistic features, alongside the subjects' identification as members of a larger group such as a tribe or society (Reynolds et al, 2001).

Such written tradition possessed and developed their own distinctive features and characteristics which appear mainly in Sīra (exemplary life story), and Tarjama (biographical interpretations or topical biography). These biographical genres were amongst the richest literature and resulted into a prolific amount of writings in pre-modern Arabic culture side by side with grammar and legal literary works. The first genre, Sīra, consists of an anecdotal narrative revolving around the exemplary life of a person who is typically a 'public' figure. The archetypal form of this type is that of the Prophet Muhammad which significantly marked the biographical genre for the succeeding centuries in terms of its originality and skill of presentation (Lunde, 2015). The genre extended over centuries to encompass the lives of rulers and other prominent religious and political figures. The most well-known examples include accounts of the life of Saladin; the heroic stories like the life of Sayf ibn Dhī Yazan al-Ḥimyarī; and the autobiography of al-Mu'ayyad fī al-Dīn Hibat Allāh al-Shīrāzī (d.1077).

The second genre, Tarjama, focusses on the achievements of 'individual' goods, and the variety of accomplishments and values embedded in the writer's life. The constituent parts of a standard Tarjama are the person's genealogy, birth date and place, teachers, travels, works, letters, and poetry, if found. Usually, a Tarjama seeks to illustrate crucial information about a person in the larger contexts providing the reader with significant and unique details about his social and intellectual circumstances as well as about his considerable role as an actor in transmitting knowledge. Its length varies between a couple of lines as a short entry of one paragraph and a dozen of pages in a biographical dictionary or historical chronicle. At times, an entire monograph is devoted to one single person.

The act of writing an individual's biography is deeply related to his merits and authority within a specific Islamic community or city. The biographical dictionaries are therefore specialized books that identify Muslim individuals within their communities or trace their professional career. The logic of composing a biographical

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dictionary is, in essence, based on the claim of authority for a particular individual or group, like jurists, within the larger community. Even the dictionaries based on a particular city are related to the 'authority' of some places as regional centres for semi-independent dynasties. The assertion of authority in such texts frequently done through two main steps: first an emphasis on the individual's connection with the chain of previous generations, and second enunciation of his or her contributions particularly the written works. In other words, the authority, mainly a religious one, is based on the active role of connecting oneself to earlier generations and through transmitting knowledge to the following generations (Qādī, 1995; Stewart, 2008).

Both terms *Sīra* and *Tarjama* were utilized by the autobiographers who produced much of their texts within the umbral of biographical writings. The majority of the autobiographical writings are, therefore, to be found within the biographical genres. This is exactly the main reason why autobiography, despite being

recognized as a distinct way of writing, never became a 'science' of its own. The main difference between the two genres is assumably the role of the narrative in presenting the life as story in autobiographies (Reynolds et al, 2001). Within this context, the variety of the pre-modern (auto)biographical literature could be classified according to different criteria, the first of which length: a short treatise, an introduction of one book, a conclusion attached to a book, short or long entry in biographical dictionary, or a separate single volume. It could be also classified according to the way of transmission: oral such as *lfi* or slander report and written ones like the bulk of autobiographies. Another effective classification which is utilized by the majority of scholars is based on topics: spiritual or Sufi autobiographies like al-Ghazālī (d. 1111); political such as the Memoirs of 'Abd Allah ibn Buluggīn (d. after 1094), and intellectual as Jalāl al-Dīn al-Suyūṭī (d. 1505). These types are in essence interlinked and inseparable, but the classification is according to the main orientation of the author

(Buḥayrī, 2018). The established division of society into *rijāl al-qalam*, men of the pen, and *rijāl al-sayf*, men of the sword, can be utilized here to easily classify any pre-modern Arabic autobiography into one of these two categories. For instance, the autobiographies of Ḥunayn ibn Iṣḥāq (d. 877) and al-Suyūṭī are ascribed to the first group, while the autobiographies of Ibn Buluggīn and Usāma ibn Munqidh (d. 1188) are placed in the second category (Lunde, 2015).

The motivations for writings an autobiography are several but we can discern four reasons why an individual presents his life to a broader audience. These are: recounting God's blessings; introducing a meaningful and exemplary life to pursue; the basic informational value; and providing a self-authored text for later biographers and historians. Among these reasons, the first two stand in contrast with the modern recognition of autobiography as confessions. Recounting God's blessings, in particular, is a rhetorical strategy that generally used to justify the act of writing an autobiography. Nearly all pre-

modern autobiographers cited the Quranic verse: *Wa 'ammaa bi niamaṭi Rabbika fahaddis* (and proclaim the bounty of your Lord.) (Q 93:11). For instance, it occurs in the 'political' Memoirs of Ibn Buluggīn, as well as in the title of al-Suyūṭī's intellectual autobiography (Reynolds et al, 2001; Stewart, 2007-2008). Despite being a motive in itself, recounting God's blessings became also a literary convention, and an essential form for autobiographers in their attempts to establish a balance between presenting his achievements and maintaining the Islamic social ethics of modesty and piety. This constituted a crucial ethical issue for authors. On one hand, the risk of hypocrisy, self-interest, pride, and a boastful appearance, which are grave sins according to Islamic manners. On the other hand, referring to one's achievements is essential as an evidence that gives its owner authority and status in his social and intellectual circles. This tension is commonly observed in several autobiographical texts where the writers were considerably aware of the danger of being arrogant, and,

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therefore, escaped the dilemma by perpetually recounting the bounty of God. (Stewart, 2008).

This convention was accompanied by three further main practices and strategies. The first is the narration of failure and difficulties during the author's childhood. A very large section is conventionally devoted to writers' stories about themselves as children, dealing with themes of failure, misbehaviour, punishments, and so forth. They were very aware of childhood as a distinct phase in which they still fell below the age of moral responsibilities. Therefore, it causes no harm to narrate several 'private' stories that no other biographies have access to or know it. The second convention is the narration of dreams and visions of the author. Either realistic or symbolic, dreams are frequently appeared at crucial moments of the autobiographer's life in order to guide him to make an important choice that will have an impact on his future. Almost all dreams are utilized to affirm the textual authority in which the author supports his saying by external testimony. The third practice is the poetic expression of emotion. Numerous biographical

writings, as mentioned before, contained a combination of prose and poetry. Such practice was likewise maintained in the autobiographical tradition through the uses of poetry, to express the emotional events in author's life. Poetry, therefore, was not a decorative element, but rather a formal strategy that was consistently used in different functions. It served to express deep and intense feelings or sentimental and significant moments that were difficult to convey in a plain language. Being able to eloquently compose poetry was furthermore perceived as an indication of the author's high educational level as a man who masters the literary arts like grammar and rhetoric (Reynolds et al, 2001). These conventions can be seen as the main vocabulary for performances through which pre-modern Arabic autobiographers legitimate their authority or their belonging to specific religious or intellectual group. It was necessary for an autobiographer to certify his social capital through these aforementioned forms in order to be seen an authority (Kalmbach, 2015).

By such conventions then, pre-modern Arabic autobiographers were able to represent themselves and to construct their individual identities. Several scholars have thus claimed that pre-modern Arabic autobiography is marked by the absence of the personality, the author's withdrawal from the events, and a tendency towards demonstrating the inner world (Kilpatrick, 1991). As Reynolds et al have argued (2001), these criticisms appear to be based on the modern western conceptions of self, personhood, public/private and so forth. Indeed, the pre-modern autobiographies are less personal, but they do certainly not lack individuality. The author usually refers to his individual life, and, in many examples, a strong sense of his personality appears. In fact, the brevity of reports regarding "personal" and "private" life in autobiographies are to be seen through the lens of Islamic social ethics. For instance, the authors expressed themselves in a careful choice, and this, according to Sellheim (1978), is due to the manner of al-ḥayā' "abashedness and humility" of the autobiographer to reveal personal or private stories that other people would know.

Despite the different context, Lambert-Hurley's (2013) observation of the dichotomy between historians and literary scholars on the evaluation of autobiography is applicable on pre-modern Arabic autobiographies. Historians focused mainly on the reliability, validity, and authentication of the autobiography as a historical source; while for the main focus of literary scholars has been the definition of autobiography as a genre that is distinguishable from other literary forms. Furthermore, scholars, in the case of pre-modern Arabic autobiographies, have concentrated mainly on either books or biographical reports which they described as autobiography. These, in essence, are indistinguishable from the prosaic writings of autobiography in European literatures (Kilpatrick,1991). They rarely, for instance, mentioned the autobiographical conventions in pre-modern Arabic poetry. Even though Reynolds et al have highlighted the importance of poetry within the narrative autobiographies, but they did not go further to examine what can be called "poetic pre-modern Arabic autobiography."

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The impact of technology on writing/narrating the self is another missing side in both historians' and literary scholars' studies of pre-modern autobiographies. Drawing on the British historian Francis Robinson's work, Lambert-Hurley argues that the spread of print culture among South Asian Muslims associated with a growing sense of the self (Lambert-Hurley, 2013). To some extent, and cautiously, one could argue that the production of paper in the Islamicate societies led to a wide circulation of first-person autobiographical texts written by famous figures as we can see for instance during the period of Saladin's reign (Reynolds et al, 2001).

In their analysis of pre-modern Arabic autobiographies, both types of studies have ignored the recent scholarships on self or social sciences and humanities in general. One reason for that is the nature of modern society - or the modern conceptions of self and personality - is quite different from pre-modern times. Indeed, different conceptions must not be neglected or overlooked, but, still, "Nothing That is Human is Alien." Theories such as Bourdieu's

concept of cultural, symbolic, and social capital can provide significant insight on the habitus of pre-modern autobiographers (as Kalmbach did on her studies about modern Egypt, 2015). The same could be said about the Dialogical Self Theory (DST) in which one can examine the "dynamic multiplicity of I positions" of these autobiographical texts (Buitelaar & Zock, 2013). DST is a useful analytic tool to analysis both the internal I-positions and the external I-positions. Through insisting on the metaphor of voice, DST will help the reader of pre-modern autobiographies to approach the different stories in these text in which "I" tells in different positions and from different perspectives. It allows one to locate the voices of I in its contexts; as well as to investigate each of "the internal dialogues taking place in the self between the various positions -internal, external, imaginal, or actual/real" and the "external dialogues (between individuals, between individuals and groups, and between groups)" (Buitelaar & Zock, 2013). Yet, applying the modern theories on pre-modern Arabic autobiographies requires deep reflection and exhausting thought.

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Autobiographies among anthropologists and the (non-religious) research group

By Lena Richter (ESR 2)

In the past, anthropological monographs often seemed to be timeless and stative, among others, due to the use of the “ethnographic present” and underlying positivist notions. Besides, it was mainly the research group being disclosed while the researcher remained invisible. According to Reed-Danahay (2007), this changed with the paradigm shift towards a more reflexive, postmodern, and feminist approach. The self-disclosure of the researcher became more common, including a critical (self)reflection on his/her nationality, gender, age, and socio-economic position. In other words: it was increasingly recognized how the academic and personal background impacted the analysis and writing. In addition, the use of the reflexive I made clear that observations are a selective perspective on a time-bounded situation, placed in a cross-cultural encounter. The use of “I” might evoke the misleading assumption of the lonely researcher. In practice, however, the research participants, editors, translators, and co-writers actively shape the

writing (Lambert-Hurley, 2013). Moreover, in new ethnographic writings, it becomes clear that the self is also fragmented and situated in certain contexts. In the words of Campbell (1989): the ethnographer is neither alone, nor in a cultural vacuum, but surrounded by relationships.

The reflexive turn also led to the emergence of different kinds of autobiographies, such as native anthropology, ethnic autobiography, and autoethnography. Auto-ethnographies further range from realist ethnographic writing that strove for objectivity to newer forms of autoethnographies that focus more on the personal self (Okely, 2001). Often the question of reliability, validity, and authenticity is raised. While a novel is presumed to be an invented story, autobiographies are expected to tell the truth. The “rawer” the data of the personal narrative the higher the expectations in terms of authenticity. For instance, diaries, journals, travel narratives, and letters are seen as close to the “real” experiences, while memoirs and autobiographies provide a more synthesized

account. However, there is a difference between the autobiography and the actual life experience. As Lambert-Hurley (2013) puts it: “Are we expecting fidelity to the facts of their biographies, to lived experience, to self-understanding, to the historical moment, to the social community, to prevailing beliefs about diverse identities, to the norms of autobiography as a literary genre itself?” According to her, the writing style and content of an autobiography always vary, depending on the writer, the timing, the place, and the imagined audience. The different genres often blur (Lambert-Hurley, 2013) and the chosen form and content also depend on national trends. For instance, the American approach focuses on one extraordinary person, while the European approach is more collective in nature and aims to show society as a whole by emphasizing the influence of socialization. Autobiographies offer many advantages, such as giving an insight into the complexity of human beings and providing a stage for those who have been excluded or stigmatized (Reed-Danahay, 2007). This has been

proven by Brettell (1982), Abu-Lughold (1993), and Lambert-Hurley (2013) who focus on female narratives.

An important genre of (auto) biographies are life history and life story. The life story zooms in on one aspect while life histories give a coherent narrative of one’s life (Reed-Danahay, 2007). Following Shaw’s (1980) definition, life histories share the following characteristics: 1) They include the writer’s socio-cultural context, 2) focus on the perspective of one individual, 3) have a time depth, and 4) relate to the local history. The life story can also center around one topic, such as illness, death, or emotion, and since the discovery of Malinowski’s (1967) diaries: sexuality and intimacy. Peacock and Holland (1993) point out that it is also possible to combine both in a processual approach, where the life stories are developed in relation to one life event. Life (hi)stories can be elicited or self-initiated and take the form of a biography or a diary, which provides an immediate and daily perspective. As Agrosino (1989) adds to the discussion, also

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here a combination is possible: the interactionist approach argues that life histories are the product of encounter. Recently, the focus is more and more on the interactions between ethnographer and autobiographer. According to Okely (2001), in this closer collaboration, both the researcher and the research group have become increasingly aware of the politics of representation and power relations. The research group has grown out of the role of being merely passive informants and is increasingly consulted for co-writing or revising prior to the publication. Current theoretical debates in life-history research also focus on cultural constructions of selfhood, emotions, and representation.

Using (auto)biographical approaches, often in the form of narratives and/or life (hi)stories, has also become very widespread when studying religious transformation (Van Nieuwkerk, 2018). Narratives can show for what reasons and how people gradually leave their religion. Well-known examples are Rotbaum's (1988) study "Between

Two Worlds: Issues of Separation and Identity after Leaving a Religious Community" where she looks at how the personal identity relates to the collective identity when deconverting. Also, Wright et al. (2011) analyzed autobiographical narratives in "Explaining Deconversion from Christianity: A study of Online Narratives." In general, one can distinguish between a positivist and a discursive approach. Within the positivist tradition, the narrative itself is not of interest but rather provides evidence for causal relations. While both orientations are based on narratives, how the narratives are collected, presented, and analyzed differs. Followers of the positivist orientation, such as Streib et al. (2009) apply a mixed-methods approach that combines questionnaire research with narrative interviews. Wright et al. (2011) apply the rational choice paradigm in explaining the change of religion. Scholars who follow this line of thought, use long quotes but only as examples to underline their argument, which is a causal relation. This way this analysis risks to pick from detailed and rich accounts, a few general explanatory

and simplified elements. Consequently, they leave out a big part of the narratives, on the basis that it does not serve as evidence for the causal relation. However, the narrative self might play a role in the process of leaving religion. It is not only a research method but also a cultural mechanism to make sense of one's life: narrations help to re-conceptualize one's religious situation. Therefore, only full narratives provide a full understanding. On a positive note, this approach can provide an idea of the typical patterns that are at stake when leaving religion.

The discursive approach focuses on the social and psychological factors behind leaving religion and how the narrator uses language to make sense of his or her situation. According to Gooren (2010), deconversion is about finding meaning, whether that is atheism or religion. It is the process where a person reflects on the religious context it is embedded and the social factors that are at stake. Discourse analysts pay more attention to the performative and discursive aspects of

narratives. According to Keane (2008) changing or losing belief is an emotionally loaded topic, therefore, the narrator will make use of gestures, facial expressions, and direct quotations to tell the story. Consequently, it is important to look at the role of language and speech, including the use of stylistic devices such as metaphors and figuration. From this perspective, leaving religion can be conceptualized as moving away from the institutional, cultural, and communal territory of the religion and (continuously) replacing it with a new set of images and ideas and beliefs. Ideally, one should pursue a mixed-method approach that combines the strong points of the positivist and discursive approach.

The approach of life-stories has been often linked with identity theories, such as the dialogical self and selfhood. Buitelaar (2006) has combined intersectionality with the formation of identity by looking at the (dis)continuation of the voices of the parents and the different I-positions of the daughters in finding their

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religious selves. Vliek (2019; 2020) has broadened the application of the dialogical self-theory on people who leave Islam. In her work on former Muslims in the Netherlands and the UK, she has pointed out that during the leaving trajectory the self relates to the significant others, as well as to different discourses ranging from religion to politics. When using narratives it is important to keep in mind that leaving religion can be described as more abrupt, all-changing, coherent, and one-directional as narratives are constructed retrospectively and are adapted to the aim, the audience, and the moment of narrating. In the process of storytelling false coherence and consistency, often structured around the turning point when one left religion, is created. For example, narrators situate elements of the new non-religious views into the period before the turning point in terms of doubts and argue that the “authentic self” could not yet be expressed. In addition, the narratives often mix personal views and experiences with the often internalized, hegemonic narrative of (leaving) Islam. For

instance, the position of women in Islam might not play a huge role for every narrator, but as it is part of the discourse, it is almost always mentioned as one of the reasons to leave Islam. Hence, one has to take into account the personal and collective narratives. However, the actual, empirical process is more complex and intertwined with other questions, that are not necessarily religious (Vliek, 2020). In this respect, it is important to include moments of doubt, ambiguity, and contradiction (Lee, 2015). Thus, to deconstruct the sharp and binary contrast between before and after this turning point, it is important not only to illustrate the departing point and the current state of non-belief, but also the ongoing journey (Van Nieuwkerk, 2018). To illustrate this further, the narratives can be combined with non-religious trajectories, that show the multidirectional, ambiguous, and fluid nature of religiosity.

The use of autobiographies and narratives to express themselves is also very common among former Muslims themselves. For instance, the book “Nieuwe

vrijdenkers” (van der Ham & Benhammou, 2018) collects twelve narratives from former Muslims from different countries who grew up in the Netherlands. The English twin exemplar might be “Leaving Faith Behind: The journeys and perspectives of people who have chosen to leave Islam” (Mughal & Saleem, 2018). Other autobiographies are “The Atheist Muslim: A Journey from Religion to Reason” (Rizvi, 2016) and *Infidel* (Ali, 2007). In the Moroccan context, Hicham Nostik (2020) published the autobiographical book “Dialogue with the Muslim in me”. Recently, also digital forms of narratives emerged, for instance, blogs (e.g. *il7ad*), YouTube channels (e.g. *kafer maghribi*), and podcasts (e.g. *Secular Jihadists*). Also (auto)biographical films of former Muslims become more common, such as “Betty/ Letter 4049: F”, a movie about the non-religious activist and founder of the MALI movement Ibtissame Betty Lachgar. While it is possible to publish under a pseudonym most of these autobiographies are narrated by well-known, public, and outspoken non-believers.

Digitalization gave space for virtual selves (Evans, 2013) and made autobiographies for a larger group possible. While not everyone might have the opportunity to write a book, it is relatively easy to create a post on Facebook or Twitter. This way, autobiographies did not only become more accessible but also changed in form. For instance, people might more frequently, interactively, and shortly express their thoughts and feelings instead of a classical monograph. However, the majority of former Muslims, prefer to share their stories only in private, for example in closed Facebook groups. In these safe spaces, out of the sight of family members or political surveillance, they can share their intimate thoughts and experiences. Yet, questions remain if these new digital forms of self-expression are truly inclusive. For instance, if female non-believers use the opportunity to express themselves online, as much as their male counterparts.

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All in all, within the field of anthropology in general and leaving religion in particular, autobiographies became more common. They are not only used by ethnographers but also by the research group itself, which then again becomes potential material to analyze for the fieldworker. Especially, life stories and life histories can illustrate the complex journey of leaving Islam and show personal as well as collective narratives. This way an individual trajectory is placed within a certain context and related to the personal background of the person. Recently, more digital forms of autoethnographies emerged, which made it more accessible for a larger group of non-believers to express themselves.

Part 3.

Are MENA women “too relational” to self-express? A journey Towards Cyber-activism Before and During the Arab Spring

By Rayane al Rammal (ESR 3)

There seems to exist a popular typology in Culture studies to arrange cultures following a binary paradigm: On the one hand we find allegedly individualist cultures (mainly the West) in which independent and bounded persons strive for personal self-enhancement while valuing most precious autonomy. On the other hand, the rest of the world is deemed to make part of a collectivist culture in which interdependent persons are created with “fluid boundaries”. They accept norms and hierarchies and value relatedness (Buitelaar, 2014). Marjo Buitelaar argues that such distinction results in a discursive selfing and othering in which a Western self-determining subject is pitted against the other non-Western subjectivities that are “not yet enlightened” because they submit to social groups and/or are obedient to religious collectivity. This is presumed to overrule their agency as individuals. Buitelaar notices that this split is built upon distorted stereotyping premises and then contends that

cultures and selves should not be viewed as either independent or interdependent, but as animated by tensions between group loyalties and personal ambitions. The portraying of non-Western societies as relational and collective has been often negatively biased. It has been overlooked however that this collectivity could be indispensable in challenging socio-political contexts in zones deeply affected by the exploitation of the colonising West itself.

For example, Suad Joseph (2005) found that in a social setting where state was proved to be untrustworthy and unreliable to its citizens (like most of the countries of the “Third World”), individuals felt fragile and found ultimate security in kin relations. These relations were valued above the persons, because a person’s social identity, political safety and economic well-being depended on belonging to, caring for, and being cared for by a web of relationships that were kin based or were transformed into kin-like relationships.

According to Joseph, in such social setting, a relational notion and construct of the self was valorised for effectively weaving persons together in “lifelong and life-giving bonds of sustenance”. She seeks to demonstrate however that this weaving does not lead to the effacement of the individuality. By trying to ethnographically locate the expressions of the desire of the self (not limited to sexual ones), she observed that it was channeled through these different webs of relationality. Notwithstanding, patriarchal structures and processes led to different enactments of this relational self, privileging generally the desires of men and seniors, renouncing those of juniors and women. The latter (non-Western women) appears to be a category worth examining in terms of manifesting the selfhood since these women are often presumed to be silent and secluded.

Siobhan Lambert-Hurley (2013) raises for example the important question of whether, in a highly patriarchal and deeply

religious context like South Asia, women had the ability to self-express or whether the women’s identities were simply “too relational” to others in this period to participate in a genre, like autobiography, supposedly “defined by the emphasis on the self”. She concluded that in the process of attending to women voices in the form of autobiographies, one has to expand her circle of search and be attuned to the many possibilities to be included under the labels of personal narratives like novels, travelogues, reformist literature, letters, diaries and ghosted narratives etc. Lambert-Hurley got inspiration in her research from historian Francis Robinson’s indication that the rise of print among South Asian Muslims initiated a “process of interiorization” reflected in “the expression of “a growing sense of self” and the “manifold nature of the human individual”, thus crediting this technological tool (print) for the rise and the expression of the self in the many (sub)genres that she found.

Part 3.

Are MENA women “too relational” to self-express? A journey Towards Cyber-activism Before and During the Arab Spring

By Rayane al Rammal (ESR 3)

More recently, a similar analytical move endowed with technological determinism was made by many scholars studying the MENA region to correlate the rise of information technologies at the beginning of the current century and the growing feminist self-expression and authority contestation following the Arab Spring. And if we want to follow Lambert-Hurley's conclusion in defining the genre of autobiographical writing for women, we might want to include Facebook posts, tweets, Instagram pictures and YouTube videos to the women's personal narratives. Hayton (2009) explores for example the coalescence of personal blogging with traditional theories of autobiography. He proposes that the internet offers a rich arena for the written self, where the traditions of conventional autobiography can exist alongside more permeable but equally valid life-writing platforms. In especially the third wave of feminism, many theorists posited that women's cultural production of sharing personal experience especially

in autobiography, is in itself a political act and at the core of authority contestation (Heywood, 2006;). Hence cyber-activism, which has at its core blogs and social media, can function as an autobiographical platform for women's self-expression. However, the road of the introduction to these technologies to women in the Arab World have been rough and bumpy.

According to Fatima Mernissi (2006), two words were used to describe the boom of usage of digital technologies when they first appeared in the Arab World: *al-fitna al-raqqmiyya* (digital chaos) and *ishtiyah* (invasion). They threatened to lead to the collapse of the space frontiers that divided the universe into a private sheltered arena, where women and children were supposed to be protected, and a public where adult male exercised their presumed problem-solving authority. Many Imams, all over the Arab World, were alarming crowds (mainly adult male believers) to the fact that Arab women and youth now

navigate freely on the web and communicate intimately with strangers, escaping religious and parental censorship. They subsequently warned that these technological tools helped propel allegedly western values of “solitude, narcissism, and hatred of the other”, that were jeopardising the relational Muslim self (Mernissi, 2006). Moreover, early 2000s statistics showed that the internet revolution left many Arab women's lives untouched because of the lack of access, unfamiliarity with computers, illiteracy, and a shortage of access points that are gender friendly, are some of the explanations offered for the gendered nature of the Arab digital divide (Wheeler, 2017). In the decade preceding the Arab Spring, internet access in the region expanded from these negligible levels to 40 percent of the Arab population by 2010 (Fact Sheet, 2011). As the uprisings grew, the number of these users increased drastically by 68 percent mainly comprising the Youth population (Radsch & Khamis, 2013). Arab women however constituted only a third of these users. While these

numbers are unequivocally small, they are far from nugatory or futile. Many scholars have sought to study women's cyber-activism during the Arab Spring (Khamis, S. & Vaughn, K. 2011; Radsch, 2012; Newson & Lengel, 2012; Landorf, 2014; Gheyntanhi & Moghadam, 2014; Guta & Karolak, 2015;) and to show the importance of these platforms for women empowerment in the region. They shed light on how young Arab women used cyber-activism to participate in the wave of socio-political transformations of the Arab Spring. They argued that these activists (although not representing the totality of the population of Arab Women of the MENA region) “leveraged social media to enact new forms of leadership, agency, and empowerment” (Radsch & Khamis, 2013). Since the public space is still in many ways non-welcoming to them and since many of them have caretaking responsibilities which does not award them the privilege of participating in demonstrations (Winegar, 2012).

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However, the impact of the Arab spring revolutions-cyber-activism included- on women's rights in the Arab World has been challenged by many feminist scholars including Arab ones (Brown, 2011; Younis, 2011) and is still to be investigated more profoundly and more critically.

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